

IMPACT OF SELF ESTEEM ON PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING AMONG SINGLE ADULTS IN PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to determine the impact of self Esteem on Psychological Well-being among Single adults in Pakistan. The current study was comprised of total participants N= 175 out of which n=114 were females and n=61 were males, who aged between 20 – 35 years (M=24.68, S.D= 3.059). The convenient sampling technique has been used to collect the sample. The tools have been used in this study are as following, Index of Self Esteem Scale (SES) (Rosenberg, M, 1965) and Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-being Scale (WEMWBS) ((Fishwik, et.al, 2007) for Self-esteem and psychological well-being respectively. It was hypothesized that there would be significant relationship between Self-Esteem and Psychological Well-being among single adults and age would have negative correlation with Self-Esteem. There would also be gender differences in self-esteem and psychological well-being. The findings of current study revealed that there is positive but moderate relationship between self-esteem and psychological well-being, whereas second hypothesis of this study was rejected and findings has revealed that age is positively correlated with self-esteem but relationship has been found weak. Findings has also revealed that there is gender differences between self-esteem and psychological well-being. Females have scored low on self-esteem and psychological well-being comparatively to males. Since, females perceive more societal pressure and stress because of not getting married on prime and right age. However, males have different perspective regarding marriage and they focus more on career establishment till this age. Current study has implications in clinical settings and in personal growth along with subjective well-being.

Keywords: Self-esteem, psychological well-being, mental well-being, single adults, unmarried adults

INTRODUCTION

Many social-learning theorists, including Morris Rosenberg, defined self-esteem in terms of a stable sense of personal worth or worthiness. Inherited personality traits and childhood experiences shape the way one interpret their life events. That in turn affect our self-esteem. Other factors impacting

upon self-esteem include painful events/experiences such as bereavement, divorce, serious illness or bullying (Edelman, 2007).

In our Pakistani culture, marriage is considered as blessing. And, since, the majority of the natives are practicing Muslims, the religious belief has also

reinforced this cultural view. Because Islam also encourages a person to get married, as soon as a person reaches puberty. The societal pressure to get married at what is considered prime time leads to many issues in the person's life. They usually face rejection from their immediate family. They subsequently develop feelings of dejection, desperation, and worthlessness. The notion of getting married at a time that's culturally desirable (East, 1998; Settersten & Hagestad, 1996), and deviating from preferred course pathways can also be stressors that in turn negatively affect one's mental health (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984; Neugarten, 1979). In our society, as in most Asian societies, remaining unmarried is a stigma. It has also been explored and it was found out that people do in fact marry in order to avoid the said stigma and for the monetary rewards (Pearlin & Johnson, 1977).

It has been well noted in the literature that marriage benefits mental health. In fact, marriage provides one with several psychosocial and economic resources that are associated with high levels of well-being. First, the marital role is a potential source of meaning and purpose (Marks, 1996) that provide a sense of mattering to others (Schieman & Taylor, 2001; Taylor and Turner, 2001). Long ago, Durkheim (1897, 1951), proposed that the rate of married people committing suicide was significantly lower due to their higher social integration, protection from life strains, a sense of security, meaningfulness and purpose. Many studies since then show that marriage is associated with less morbidity, mortality, mental illness, substance abuse and distress (e.g., Adler, 1953; Bloom, Asher, & White, 1978; Gove, 1972; Ross, Mirowsky, & Goldstein, 1990; Waite, 1995). Indeed, one survey of the literature states that no social variable is more consistently or more powerfully related with the distribution of psychopathology than marital status (Bloom et al., 1978). Another survey concludes that one of four major social patterns of distress is that "married people are less distressed than unmarried ones" (Mirowsky & Ross, 1989). Marriage provides higher level of social integration and supported compared to being unmarried. Lastly, a married person can share economic resources, something not possible if one stayed

unmarried (Waite, 1995). So, it is well established that married adults typically far better in terms of health and well-being than the unmarried (Carr & Springer, 2010). Married adults in their 50s tend to experience lower levels of psychological distress, including depression and anxiety, than do the unmarried (Marks, 1996; Waite, 1995; Waite & Gallagher, 2000).

Gender plays a central role in the perception of the effect of marital status. It appears to have a larger association with well-being for man than for women (Gove, Hughes, & Style, 1983). Both male and female need a companion in life. For companionship, social support and to fulfill the innate need to have a family. Research suggests that men have more desire for marriage than do women because they have less social support (Frazier, Arikian, Benson; 1996). The same study also noted that never married individuals have more desire for marriage and lower life satisfaction than divorced individuals because they have lower life satisfaction than divorced individuals because they have lower self-esteem. Females are left neglected thus suppressing their moral and confidence to share their views and leaving them to experience either major depressive disorder or diagnosable symptoms. Such symptoms include isolation, mood swings, aggressiveness, crying spells, general unhappiness, loss of concentration and lethargy (Whitton; 2007). Cohabitation is not enough, in fact, for better mental health, marriage is necessary. And this benefit is larger for men than for women (Gove et al., 1983). Married young adults report low rates of drunkenness, higher life satisfaction compared to those who have no relationship and have not married (Jeremy, 2012). Theories of partnership status as a continuum of social attachment (Ross, 1995) and commitment (Kamp, Dush & Amgato, 2005) would lead us to expect that older married individuals enjoy the highest levels of well-being, followed by cohabitators, daters, and lastly single individuals. Normative life course theoretical perspective (Neugarten, Moore, & Lowe, 1968) suggests that social and cultural age norms for marital transition inform one's personal preference for age at marriage. Guided by these norms, which vary across social groups (East, 1998; Settersten & Hagestad, 1996), people "develop a concept of the

normal expectable life cycle, a set of anticipations that certain life events will occur at a certain time, and a mental clock telling them whether they are on or off time" (Neugarten, 1979). This theory is most in keeping with our study because people of Pakistan are basically guided by our strict norms regarding marriage culturally. Exceeding the age bracket that is deemed unacceptable in our society leads to the feeling of social isolation at times that in turn effect the mental well-being. Being rejected because of this will lead to negative effect on our self-esteem. Because mostly, one is compared to someone who has entered a new life transition (getting married, giving birth). Entering a new life transition (e.g., getting married or having a child) is a pivotal point in a person's life that shapes self-concept. If it's off-time or at an undesirable event occurs, it will negatively affect well-being. Because it's depriving one of a comparable peer support. It's also depriving one of the satisfaction and meaning, and thus the psychological benefit, an on-time transition could provide. It may leave one ill prepared for a particular role, producing role strain. Lastly, and most important, keeping in mind our cultural norm, it damages or at the least negatively effects our social network. This societal sanction will have a damaging effect on our self-esteem. From the perspective of this theory, individuals who have never married, who have deviated from their perceived age of marriage, violate age norms for marriage, suffer identity crisis and suffer from negative social sanction (Sharp & Ganing, 2007).

Stress process theory (Pearlin, 1989) is another framework to understanding how an off time transitions, (late or early), undermine our psychological well-being. As the name suggests, life event stressors are of particular relevance in understanding this process. The degree to which life events and transitions (e.g., getting married) negatively or positively affects us depends mostly on how we appraise them (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984 & Pearlin, 1989). Although distress tied to any particular life event may be short lived (Wheaton & Montazer, 2010), the negative mental health consequences of off-time transitions may endure, resulting in the proliferation of

stressors and distress over the life course (Pearlin, 1989). From a stress perspective, for someone who has never married or has past the desired age for marriage, may have a 'nonevent stressor'. A nonevent stressor is the absence of a desired, normative or scheduled event (Wheaton & Montazer, 2010). 'Role captivity', is a chronic, enduring stressor that occurs when an individual unwillingly occupies a role or status (Pearlin, 1989). In the present study, non-event stressor would not be able to get married and role captivity is being in the state of unmarried. A never married individual has moved beyond their desired age at marriage, they will perceive their marital status as a larger violation of life course and experience it as a nonevent stressor and an increasing form of role captivity. By this theory, a person is not necessarily being rejected. In fact, said person mental health is effected by the stress and so being in the role captivity state he would sometimes unknowingly effect his relationship with his peers. When his social relations are effected and peer support is lacking, the person's self-esteem would be negatively affected.

The present study aimed to determine the impact of self-esteem on psychological well-being among single adults in Pakistan. Therefore, self-esteem is independent variable and psychological well-being is dependent variable. It was hypothesized that self-esteem has direct positive relationship with psychological well-being. On the basis of assumptions, when self-esteem levels would be increased, it would enhance mental health. . Therefore, when an individual is single or unmarried, he or she can experience low self-esteem because of societal pressure, their psychological health can also be negatively affected. The drawbacks of being single or unmarried manifest indications of depression among females and substance abuse among men (Barrett, 2000; Simon, 2002; Umberson et al. 1996 & Williams, 2003), and they experience relatively more psychological distress than married people (Barrett, 2000; Marks & Lambert, 1998; Menaghan & Lieberman, 1986; Waite & Gallagher, 2001).

Significance of study

The significance of present study is that it would provide mental health Practitioners extensive understanding about their clients in a better and deeper way. Self-esteem has profound impact on individual's mental health and it also helps in enhancing psychological well-being as well as personal growth and interpersonal relationships which results in healthy self-image and contentment with life. Marriage has been considered as pivotal for broader, positive self-image & self-esteem and having sound mental health, which avoids other psychological problems like distress & depression etc. Therefore, this study has based on single adults who have never married to explore the impact of self-esteem and its relationship with psychological well-being and how it is affected by age in Pakistani culture. Through present study, it would be understood that people who does not get married on the prime age, they can suffer from low self-esteem and can have disturbed mental health. They can experience worthlessness, depression, agitation etc. Because, somehow their biological needs remained unmet and their support group becomes limited, as well

as feelings of loneliness & dejection also overwhelmed. All this can be helpful for clinical psychologists or mental health practitioners to get idea that people who have crossed age such as 35 years and are still unmarried, so marriage can be one reason of being depressed, stressed out and loneliness. As, Pakistani culture and religion also endorse marriage in great deal and this societal pressure does leave profound negative effect on individual's mental health.

Research Objectives

The current study exemplified the methodical attempt to find out the impact of self-esteem on psychological well-being among single adults in Pakistan. The main objectives of the study are;

- To examine the role of self-esteem in psychological well-being among single adults.
- To examine the relationship of age with self-esteem.
- To examine the gender differences in self-esteem and psychological well-being.

Research Questions

- What is the relationship of Self Esteem with Psychological Well-being?
- Is age negatively correlated with self-esteem?
- Is there any gender difference between Self Esteem and Psychological Well-being?

Hypotheses

H1:

- There would be a significant relationship between Self Esteem and Psychological Well-being.

H2:

- There would be negative correlation between age and self-esteem.

H3:

- There would be a significant gender differences in Self Esteem and Psychological Well-being.

Method

Research Design

The current study is quantitative correlational survey research design in which two structured self-report questionnaires were used to assess the relationship between self-esteem and psychological well-being among single adults in Pakistan.

Participants

The target population for this study was single adults. The total participants N= 175 (n=61 Males, n=114 Females) were approached from different areas of Pakistan. Convenient purposive sampling was used to approach these single adults who aged between 20 – 35 years (M=24.68, S.D= 3.059). The following Table 1 shows the frequencies and percentages of the demographic variable.

Table 1
Frequency and percentages of demographic variable (N=175)

Variables	f	%
Gender		
Males	61	34.9
Females	114	65.1
Education		
Intermediate	29	16.6
Graduation	70	40.0
Masters	46	26.3
Post-Graduation	29	16.6
Doctorate	01	0.6
Occupation		
Students	74	42.3
Professional	52	29.7
Student & Professional	38	21.7
Unemployed	10	5.7
Other	01	0.6
Marital Status		
Single Adults	175	100
Socioeconomic Status		
Lower	02	1.1
Middle	165	94.3
Upper	07	4.0
Age (in years)		
20-35	20	34

The above-mentioned Table 1 shows the frequency distribution and the percentages of all the demographic variables that were considered in the present study and the focus of the study was to target the true representative sample of the population in the current study.

Measures

Demographic information form: In the light of above mentioned literature review following demographics had been included in the study: the participant's name, age, gender, education, socio economic status, occupation and marital status.

Index of self Esteem (ISE)

Index of Self-esteem was developed by American social psychologist Morris Rosenberg (1965). It is 10-item scale that measures global self-worth by measuring both positive and negative feelings about the self. The scale is believed to be uni-dimensional. All items are answered using a 4-point Likert scale format ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. Items 2, 5, 6, 8, 9 are reverse scored. Give "Strongly Disagree" 1 point, "Disagree" 2 points, "Agree" 3 points, and "Strongly Agree" 4 points. Sum scores for all ten items. Keep scores on a continuous scale. Higher scores indicate higher self-esteem. The scale consistently achieves an Alpha coefficient of .90 or larger on reliability. The scale has been investigated with respect to content, construct, factorial, and known group's validity. It nearly always achieves validity coefficients of .60 or greater. Re-adaptability Statistics of this scale is Flesch reading ease: 90; Gunning's Fog Index: 6; Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level: 4.

Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-being (WEMWBS)

WEMWBS was developed through research that was conducted at Warwick and Edinburgh Universities (Fishwick, Hiller, Joseph, Platt, Brown & Tennant; 2007). The Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-being Scale (WEMWBS) comprises 14 items that relate to an individual's state of mental well-being (thoughts and feelings) in the previous two weeks. Responses are made on a 5-point scale ranging from 'none of the time' to 'all of the time'. Each item is worded positively and together they cover most, but not all, attributes of mental well-being including both hedonic and

eudemonic perspectives. Areas not covered include spirituality or purpose in life.

Cronbach's alpha coefficient = 0.89 (n = 348). Test-retest reliability is determined by calculating the correlation between two sets of scores for the same group of people who repeat the test after a set period of time. For WEMWBS, the time period was one week. Correlation $\alpha = 0.83$ after one week (n = 124) α Intra-class correlation coefficient the test-retest reliability score was high for WEMWBS after one week. This suggests that the transient fluctuations that a person may experience from one day to the next are not reflected in the scores, and these scores remain robust over a short period of time.

Procedure

The research was carried out by first getting permission to access and use the scales from the authors via email. Research data was collected through online process. Firstly, google forms were prepared and link was sent to participants through what's app, messenger and email. Before being a part of this study, participants were requested read all instruction carefully, which were written about study and then give an informed consent in which they were briefly informed about the nature and purpose of the study, and their right to withdraw from the study at any time. In addition, the participants were also assured about the confidentiality of their identity, personal information, findings and responses in written instructions of consent form. Along with this demographic sheet and two self-report questionnaires were attached to fill out. The participants were requested to carefully read the instructions given for each test before filling out the items. After the participants had completed the given questionnaires, their forms were submitted through google forms. Total 250 forms were filled by participants from different areas of Pakistan, out of which 75 forms were filled by married participants and one above age (age range was 20-35 years for this study purpose) which were excluded from data on the basis of exclusion criteria and rest of data has been used in present study on the basis of inclusion criteria (i.e., single/unmarried adults males and females aged 20-35 years). Data was then entered and

tabulated in SPSS and analysis was done to find out the relationship between the two variables.

Results

The data was analyzed with the help of SPSS. The following tables show the results of the current study and their respective interpretations.

Descriptive statistics

Demographic Information of entire data is presented for their education, socioeconomic status and occupation (Table 2a to 2c). The statistics for comparing the means including mean, standard deviation and t- test is also

exemplified in the preceding tables. The entire sample comprises N=175 participants which are further dispersed into 114 females and 61 males in which age was taken 20 to 35 years, minimum qualification was intermediate, marital status was only single adults, furthermore, socioeconomic status, upper class, middle class and lower class. However, qualification was also divided into intermediate, graduation, masters, post graduates and doctorates, whereas occupation was further divided into students, professionals, student & professionals, unemployed and other.

Table 2 (a)

In Comparing means of demographic Socioeconomic Status such as upper class, middle class & lower class (N=175), significant differences were observed in entire independent and dependent variables Self-esteem and psychological well-being ($p < 0.01$)

	SES	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	95% confidence Interval for Mean	
					Lower	Upper
Self Esteem	Upper	7	29.43	3.259	26.41	32.44
	Middle	165	28.46	4.048	27.84	29.08
	Lower	2	28.00	2.828	2.59	53.41
	Total	174	28.49	3.998	27.90	29.09
PWB	Upper	7	49.14	6.176	43.43	54.85
	Middle	165	48.30	8.751	46.95	49.64
	Lower	2	41.50	9.192	-41.09	124.09
	Total	174	48.25	8.658	46.96	49.55

*SES= Socioeconomic Status, PWB= Psychological Well being

Table 2 (b)

In Comparing means of demographic education group (N=175), significant differences were found in educational levels such as intermediate, Graduation, Masters, Post graduates and Doctorates in entire independent and dependent variables Self Esteem and Psychological well-being ($p < 0.01$)

	EDU	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	95% confidence Interval for Mean		Self
					Lower	Upper	
Esteem	INT	29	27.34	3.568	25.99	28.70	
	GRA	70	28.40	3.991	27.45	29.35	
	MAS	46	29.24	3.825	28.10	30.38	
	P.GRA	29	28.86	4.756	27.05	30.67	
	DOC	1	31.00	.	.	.	
	Total	175	28.54	4.027	27.94	29.14	

	INT	29	47.69	8.164	44.58	50.80
	GRA	70	47.49	7.636	45.66	49.31
PWB	MAS	46	48.22	9.204	45.48	50.59
	P.GRA	29	50.79	10.462	46.81	54.77
	DOC	1	56.00	.	.	.
	Total	175	48.31	8.665	47.02	49.60

*EDU= Education, INT= Intermediate, GRA= Graduation, MAS= Masters, P.GRA= Post graduation, DOC= Doctorate & PWB= Psychological Well-being.

Table 2 (c)

In Comparing means of demographic occupation group (N=175), significant differences were found in occupational levels such as students, professionals, students & professionals, unemployed and others in entire independent and dependent variables Self Esteem and Psychological well-being ($p < 0.01$)

	OCC	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	95% confidence Interval for Mean	
					Lower	Upper
Self Esteem	STU	74	28.08	4.200	27.11	29.05
	PRO	52	29.29	4.113	28.14	30.43
	S&P	38	28.79	3.821	27.53	30.05
	UNEM	10	27.60	2.221	26.01	29.19
	6	1	23.00	.	.	.
	Total	175	28.54	4.027	27.94	29.14
PWB	STU	74	47.82	9.342	45.66	49.99
	PRO	52	47.92	8.627	45.52	50.32
	S&P	38	50.18	7.822	47.61	52.32
	UNEM	10	47.50	6.786	42.65	52.35
	6	1	41.00	.	.	.
	Total	175	48.31	8.665	47.02	49.60

*OCC= Occupation, STU= Student, PRO= Professional, S&P= Student & Professional, UNEM= Unemployed, PWB=Psychological well-being.

Table 3
 Descriptive statistics of Self Esteem and Psychological Wellbeing

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
				Statistics	Std. Error	Statistics	Std. Error
Self Esteem Total Score	175	28.54	4.027	-.023	.184	.681	.365
Psychological Wellbeing total Score	175	48.31	8.665	-.508	.184	.677	.365

The above-mentioned Table 3 shows that as per the values of Mean, Standard Deviation, Skewness and Kurtosis, the data is normally distributed.

Table 4
 Pearson Moment Product Correlations between Self-esteem, psychological well-being and age in unmarried adults (N=175)

	Self Esteem	PWB	Age (20-35)
Self -Esteem Sig (1- tailed)	1	.642**	.169*
Psychological wellbeing Sig (1- tailed)	.642**	1	.029

Age (20-35) .169* .029 1
Sig (1-tailed)

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed)

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed)

*PWB= Psychological Well being

The above table 4 mentioned that there is significant moderate positive correlation between self-esteem and psychological well-being. Moreover, age has significantly weak positive correlation with self-esteem.

Table 5
Simple Linear Regression Analysis showing variance by self-esteem and Psychological well-being

	Well-being					
	β	B	t	p	R ²	ΔR^2
Self-Esteem	.642a	1.382	11.020	.00	.412	.409

a. Predictors: (Constant), self-esteem total score

Note. β =Standardized beta, R²=R-Squared, ΔR^2 = Adjusted R-squared

Above Table 5 provides that a unit change in the predictor variable of self-esteem will result in a significant change in the criterion variable which is Psychological well-being, with a predictive percentage of 41%. The regression analysis shows there was a significant relationship was found between self-esteem and Well-being.

Table 6
Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for Linear Regression Psychological well-being is dependent of Self Esteem (N=175)
ANOVA a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	5387.953	1	5387.953	121.442	.000b
Residual	7675.384	173	44.366		
Total	13063.337	174			

a. Dependent Variable: Psychological well-being total score

b. Predictors: (Constant), self-esteem total score

Table 7
Coefficients (a) for Linear regression Psychological Well-being is dependent on Self Esteem (N=175)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			LB	UB
(Constant)	8.874	3.614		2.456	.015	1.1741	16.006

Self Esteem 1.382 .125 .642 11.020 .000 1.134 1.629
 Total Score

a. Dependent Variable: Psychological well-being total score

Note: LB = Lower Bound & UB = Upper Bound

Table 8

Mean Differences were found in gender (males & females) in all variables self-esteem and psychological well-being (N=175)

Group Statistics (T- Test)

	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Value
Self Esteem	Male	61	29.25	4.253	-.166
	Female	114	28.16	3.866	
PWB	Male	61	50.11	7.778	.084
	Female	114	47.34	8.988	

*PWB= Psychological Well being

The above-mentioned Table 8 shows that as per the values of Mean, Standard Deviation and P-Value of self-esteem and psychological well-being. It shows that there is significant gender difference in psychological well-being and self-esteem, because mostly in Pakistani culture females are stigmatized for being unmarried after 30 years.

Discussion

The present study aimed to identify the relationship between self-esteem and psychological well-being of single adults. It was hypothesized that there would be a significant relationship between self-esteem and psychological wellbeing. The results of the study revealed a moderate positive correlation between self-esteem and psychological well-being.

Self-esteem is quite a diverse concept and affects all domains of life. The way we evaluate our self, determines how we relate to others and strive towards our personal goals. So, it can be concluded that Self-esteem is rather a broad approach affecting our mental and social health (Mann, et.al, 2004). Self-esteem does impact at all ages but our study focuses mainly on single adults. The above hypothesis is justified from the demographics of our population. The higher education also plays vital role in enhancing self-esteem and positive psychological well-being and it is proved in this study that individuals with doctorates degrees scored high on self-esteem and on psychological well-being scale comparatively to others educational groups. Higher academic qualification gives a sense of mastery to single adults, it gives them the sense of confidence on

self. Research suggests higher academic achievement positively correlates with self-esteem (Aryana, 2010). People from upper class socioeconomic status also scored relatively higher on Self-esteem and psychological well-being scale than middle and lower class. People who belong to lower socioeconomic status usually have low self-esteem and those with higher socioeconomic status reported higher self-esteem (Francis & Jones, 1996), however, substantial relationship has been observed between low family socioeconomic status and low mental health (Hudson, 2005) and it stems out many mental health issues. Furthermore, individuals who are working have shown higher self-esteem and scored high on psychological well-being scale comparatively others who are non-working or both students and professionals. Studies have shown that females who are working they have relatively higher self esteem and scored higher on psychological well-being than nonworking women (Akram, 2017; Mary & Good, 2005). Unemployment leaves deeper effect on males and females sense of worth, self-esteem and psychological well-being and has direct connection with low self-esteem and poor mental health (Goldsmith, Veum & Darity, 1997). Another important demographic variable provides

explanation for hypothesis is age. The age range of participants 25-35, this age range is basically career focused age. People get feelings of mastery when they are working and this high sense of mastery also predicts better self-esteem (Erol, Yasmine, Orth & Ulrich, 2011). Certain personal characteristics can also affect our overall self-esteem and psychological well-being. These characteristics are well defined in a study which says that emotional stability, openness to experience, conscientiousness and extraversion can predict self-esteem in young adults (H.J & Afiqah, R, 2010).

Factors from the environment can also influence a single adult's self-esteem and psychological well-being. Such factors include support system. Marriage is also a support system but that is not the only support system, a part from that we have family as a support system, friends and colleagues as support system. The presence of these support systems also determines how we would react to certain life stressors. People with high self-esteem tends to have better social systems. In a study, it was found that self-esteem is highly correlated with support when the support system was present at the time of crises (Brown, Andrews, Harris, Adler & Bridge, 1986). And this higher self-esteem also predicts better psychological wellbeing. So, this support system affects the wellbeing indirectly through the self-esteem (Krause, 1987).

The second hypothesis of this study holds a notion that age of participants would be negatively correlated with self-esteem. However, the results of the study reject our hypothesis which says that there is a significant weak positive correlation of age with self-esteem. The reason of the present result would be that self-esteem may be stable trait and it does not get affected with age for single adults. As a person grows older the type of self-image, that individual holds about self tends to become fixed and does not fluctuate with time. Self-esteem tends to be stable over time and have trait like characteristics (Kuster & Orth, 2013).

The particular age group we approached for our study also suggests an explanation for the above-mentioned findings. The age range 25-35 is considered to be young adulthood. Young Adulthood is a time when people have become more emotionally stable. Self-esteem tends to

change over the course of lifespan and as per research it increases strongly till age 30 (Orth, Erol & Luciano, 2018). Self-esteem tends to be higher in young adulthood (Sanam Yar, 2018) and increases quickly at this time (Emamzadeh, 2018). The third hypothesis of our study was there would be significant gender differences between self-esteem and psychological well-being. The hypothesis is accepted in our study. Females scored low on self-esteem and psychological well-being as compared to males. Possible reasons could be our cultural pressure of marriage. Marriage is a very important aspect of life in our collectivistic culture. And getting married at the right age is as important as the idea of marriage. Our religion also emphasizes on getting married early, it is advised to get married after puberty as soon as possible. The reason our religion emphasizes on marriage is that it protects us from a lot of crimes such as adultery, the person if married then fulfill his/her desires through right means. The idea of marriage in Islam is to make a person settle down and not to suppress the individual (Sibtayn international foundation, 2010). Marrying at right age is also important medically because it is related to fertility. A person gets married to build a family and someone who could not make a family always desires to have one. Science reveals that women marrying after age 30 is at risk of birth complications and child is at risk of developing Down's syndrome and other related illnesses (Hayat, 2018).

From a social point of view not getting married at right time brings in a lot of hazards especially for females. Our present study included participants of age range 25-35 and mostly females are part of this study. At this particular age a female is expected to be settled and married and if not then it brings in a lot of obstacles, stigma and stressors for a female. No matter how educated and professionally sound a woman is, her worth is only judged by the number of proposals she has gotten. This spiteful negative attitude of society has led some women to become against of getting married at all (Zahidi, 2016). In Pakistan family pressure to get married, societal pressure and cultural practices affects a female's overall mental health (Niaz, 2004). Males scoring higher on self-esteem and psychological well-being again can be

explained by the age range. Since at age of 25-35 mostly males are working and building their career, they are the bread winners of family so this idea of providing family itself is enhancing self-esteem. In a study gender differences and age differences of self-esteem were explored, it was identified that self-esteem increases with age however males tend to have higher self-esteem (Bleidorn, Dennisen, Gebauer, Arslan, Rentfrow & Potter, 2016).

Female unemployment can also be the reason of above-mentioned results. This could be another important factor which influences female self-esteem. Firstly, in a country like Pakistan female earning is itself a stigma, some females are not even given right to higher education so thinking about a woman to work is far beyond. But even if some women get to get permission the environment is not flourishing, they are not given ample opportunities to work (Agencies, 2018). These all factors when combined turns to affect quite negatively a female's self-worth and self-esteem.

Conclusion

Self-esteem plays a very significant role in our lives. It influences us in every aspect of life. Our study aimed to explore the relationship between self-esteem and psychological well-being and results showed significant moderate relationship. Self-esteem tends to get affected with a lot of factors such as personal, societal, marital pressures, age and interpersonal and they all in turn affects our well-being. Most important, in our Islamic society and Pakistani culture, marriage is being considered essential for living both for females and males, in this regard, women experience more pressure from their family and society to get married at right time that is 25 years and start their family and considered as protected and empowered in comparison to single/ unmarried women. If they cross their prime age, then they can have low self-esteem and can suffer from certain mental illness like depression, stress, anxiety, disturbed interpersonal relations, self-worthlessness and loneliness, aggression etc. However, males have score relatively higher than females on both self-esteem and psychologically well-being. So, the age 35 years which is rather problematic and inducing stress in women regarding marriage, for males it is

quite right time to get married, since they have established their careers till this age and they are ready to get married, get settled and make their own families.

Recommendations

- Cognitive behavioral therapy interventions can be used to enhance single adult's self-esteem and psychological well-being.
- Future researches can be done with different age groups to compare the data for understanding the concepts of self-esteem and psychological well-being more deeply.

Limitations

- Sample size was small which limits generalizability.
- Online medium was used in which responses may not be given attentively.
- Mood of participants at the time of filling form may have affected study results.

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